

Diffusion technology as a tool for characterizing and enhancing germination of maize (*Zea mays. L*) genotypes^ψ

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Abstract : Diffusion technology employed earlier for characterizing seed genotypes and the theory of water diffusivity recently developed has now been further extended and tested for enhancing germination of two promising maize (*Zea mays. L*) genotypes viz. BH-660 and Pop-902 × 903. The values of the seed constant obtained clearly showed that the two maize genotypes were genetically different, not only from one another but also from the four Indian maize genotypes, viz. Paras, Parkash, Parbhat and Kesri. The water diffusivities at 25 °C were found to be $0.0651 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.0556 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively indicating that the diffusion rate of water in BH-660 was 1.2 times greater than that in Pop-902 × 903, and that it absorbed nearly 11.1% more water than the latter genotype. Field trials results showed an increase of 8% and 2% in seed germination when the seeds of the two genotypes were sown after these were subjected to water diffusion at 25 °C and steady-state conditions obtained in the laboratory. These studies distinctly demonstrated that the critical moisture content, biochemical and physiological activities attained under the steady-state conditions during water diffusion bore a direct relation with critical time for seed germination, defined earlier and experimentally tested for selected seed genotypes of different crops. The technology so developed can be fruitfully exploited with seeds of other maize genotypes, as well as crops.

Keywords : Germination of maize, diffusion technology.

Diffusion as a technology has been seldom directly correlated experimentally with seed germination although it is clear that water diffusivity plays a key role in germination process¹⁻⁵. Further no attempt was ever made to differentiate between the time of germination (t_g), as reported by Phillips¹ and the critical time for germination (t_{cig}), the concept which has been introduced recently and tested experimentally for proper seed germination^{8,9}. In our earlier studies, two different approaches were followed to determine water diffusivity in germinating seed. In one of this a seed was soaked in excess amount of water and diffusion process carried out until steady-state conditions were achieved, whereas in the second case limited and calculated amount of water was made to diffuse into the seed so as to attain a specific targeted moisture content greater than the initial value. Since whole of this water diffused into the seed within a specific time, steady-state conditions cannot be attained in the later case. In order to determine water diffusivity a theory and dif-

fusion cell apparatus was recently developed for the former case whereas an empirical relation developed for the latter. The validity of the theory and the empirical relation was established by performing diffusion experiments with wheat and soybean genotypes⁶⁻⁹. In our earlier studies a theory of diffusion concerning electrolytes and non-electrolytes was also developed and procedure developed to characterize seed on the basis of a new constant viz. seed constant, which is a characteristics of seed membrane/coat and physiological nature^{6,7,10}. Seeds of different crops varieties were characterized on this basis and diffusion rates of some simple valence salts also determined^{6-8,12,13}.

Keeping in view the importance of diffusion studies and the technology so developed for characterizing seeds it becomes very important to extend the recently developed theory of water diffusivity⁹ and estimating the critical time for germination (t_{cig}) and co-relating it with germination and crop yield. Thus the present study was un-

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dertaken with the following objectives :

- (i) To carry out water diffusion studies using the theory and methodology recently developed when seed is made to germinate in excess water and to determine water diffusivities for two maize genotypes viz. BH-660 and Pop-902 × 903 at 25 °C.
- (ii) To characterize the maize genotypes on the basis of seed constants by employing the methodology developed earlier.
- (iii) To compare the experimental procedure used by Phillips¹ of wiping the seed(s) for determining the weight(s) with the present one in which no wiping was done for calculating the diffusion coefficients.
- (iv) To determine the critical time for germination (t_{ctg}) for the two maize varieties.
- (v) To carry out field trials with seeds of the above maize genotypes by carrying out laboratory diffusion studies after steady-state conditions are attained and finally.
- (vi) To establish the co-relation between critical time for germination (t_{ctg}), seed germination and water diffusivity.

Theory :

The theory of water diffusivity⁹ in which Fick's law has been restated in terms of particle density gradient in place of concentration gradient/water potential¹¹ is mathematically related to the flux and diffusion constant (D) as

$$J(t) = -D \left[\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right] / N_A \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of water molecules per unit volume and N_A is the Avogadro's constant. For diffusion in germinating seed the theory developed relates the average integral diffusion coefficient, \bar{D} , by the equation

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{seed} t} \ln \frac{\Delta N_0}{\Delta N_f} \quad (2)$$

where β_{seed} is the seed constant defined by

$$\beta_{seed} = \frac{A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) \quad (3)$$

in which A and l are the effective area and pore length of the seed membrane/coat and V_1 and V_2 are the volumes of the water and that of the seed respectively. $\Delta N_0 = N_1 - N_2$ and $\Delta N_f = N_3 - N_4$ are the initial and final number of water molecules before and after the diffusion process and t is the time of diffusion in seconds. Therefore, for determining \bar{D} , β_{seed} , t , ΔN_0 and ΔN_f must be known.

Determination of seed constant (β_{seed}) :

Eq.(3) defines the seed constant with A , l , V_1 and V_2 . But the seed constant cannot be directly estimated by this equation as it not possible to determine A and l precisely. Therefore an alternative procedure has to be used. In our earlier studies⁶ seed constant was determined by diffusing a reference electrolyte, 0.01 M KCl into seed for which the exact value of \bar{D} in water is known. This was necessary since the exact \bar{D} for water in a seed is not known.

The procedure to determine the seed constant and the experimental apparatus and the theory of diffusion developed for electrolytes/non-electrolytes are given elsewhere^{6,10}. It is important to note that seed constant of a seed can be determined by employing any suitable concentration of KCl in addition to the 0.01 M KCl as quoted in our earlier paper^{6,10}. However, we retain this concentration as one of the best options for all seed constants determination for uniformity. In the present study, seed constant of BH-660 and Pop-902 × 903 maize (*Zea mays. L*) genotypes was determined by using 0.01 M KCl at 25 °C.

Procedure — Water diffusion experiment with maize (Zea mays. L) genotypes :

(i) Diffusion cell :

The diffusion cell designed earlier¹⁰ and modified⁶ later was employed in the present study. The cell employed has a volume of 13.50 ml and in order to have reproducibility in seed constant and \bar{D} values one must have a cell with a fixed volume. This fact has been discussed in an earlier paper⁷⁻⁹.

(ii) Diffusion runs with water and determination of \bar{D} at 25 °C :

Maize seeds of BH-660 and Pop-902 × 903 genotypes having initial moisture contents of 7% and 7.7% respectively were procured from the Department of Plant Science, Alemaya University, Ethiopia and preserved in air tight containers at room temperature. From these lots seeds having nearly constant weights (up to third place of decimal) for each genotype were carefully selected and a

single grain was used for each water diffusion experiments at 25 ± 0.5 °C. The diffusion cell was thoroughly cleaned and dried. The seed was then carefully inserted into the bottom of the cell with the help of a pair of clean tweezers so that no injury was caused to it. Vacuum was then applied for few minutes in order to remove the trapped air from the pores of the seed. The cell was next filled with pure water having a conductance of ~ 49 μS and which was thermo-stated before hand. The B-19 standard joint of the diffusion cell to which high quality silicon grease was slightly applied, was slowly and carefully inserted so that no air bubbles remained in the cell. The cell was then thermo-stated in an upright position maintained at 25 ± 0.5 °C and the diffusion run timed from this point. After the attainment of steady-state conditions the experiment was stopped and time for diffusion recorded. The monitoring of steady-state conditions was on the basis of seed exudation process and the details for which are discussed elsewhere⁷⁻⁹. After the diffusion experiment the cell was removed from the thermostat and the seed taken out carefully with the help of a fine clean tweezers. Utmost care was taken to remove the B-19 male joint from the cell so that no water droplets remained sticking on it. In addition, the seed with the tweezers was carefully handled and this was then given few slight jerks over the mouth of the diffusion cell so that every excess droplets of water sticking on its surface falls back into it. In one of the earlier studies (Phillips¹) the seeds were weighed after these were removed from the water and quickly blotted on a cotton towel to remove excess water. In order to check the difference in diffusion rates due to this method of using cotton towel for removing excess surface water, two different approaches were made in the present study while taking the final weight of the seed. In one approach seed was wiped with clean tissue paper quickly after it was removed from the cell as was done by Phillips¹ and final weight recorded immediately whereas in the second replicated experiment with the seed of same weight no wiping (except some jerks which were considered to be suitable for removing excess surface water) was done and final weight taken. Once the final weight of the seed in the two separate experiments were taken eq. (2) was used to determine \bar{D} since β_{seed} , time, t in seconds, initial and final weights of water (g) from which N_1 , N_2 , N_3 and N_4 , can be easily determined by the use of simple relation quoted earlier^{8,9}. In Table 2 are recorded the initial and final weights (W_1 , W_2 , W_3 and W_4) of water (g), the initial and final number (N_1 , N_2 , N_3 and N_4) of water molecules and the quantities $\Delta N_0 = N_1 - N_2$ and $\Delta N_f = N_3 - N_4$, the \bar{D} values obtained without and

after wiping the seed and also the mean \bar{D} for both the two maize genotypes at 25 °C. Three replicated diffusion experiments were carried out and the \bar{D} values recorded are the average of these.

Results and discussion

(i) Characterization of maize genotypes :

The seed constant (β_{seed}) as defined by eq. (2) is a characteristic of seed membrane/coat and therefore any two seeds which are different genetically will have different seed constant. This fact was supported by experimental evidence when seed constants of different wheat, maize, chickpea and soybean genotypes were determined^{6-9,12,13}. Seed constant is now considered as a more complex constant and its determination from diffusion experiment is not only related to seed characteristics but also has its physiological contribution. In the present work the seed constants of BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903 maize genotypes were determined and the values obtained were 105.1×10^{-3} and 132×10^{-3} respectively at 25 °C. Since these values are different from each other, it clearly indicated that the two maize genotypes are genetically different and hence are the "finger prints" of the genotypes. A comparison of the seed constants obtained for four different Indian maize genotypes (Table 1) further supported the above facts, as these were all different from those obtained for BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903. It is also to be noted that diffusion technology can now provide a method to "finger print" seeds on the basis of seed constants.

(ii) Water diffusivity :

From a glance at the data recorded in Table 2 the percentage variation in the final weights of water without and after wiping the seeds on the completion of the diffusion experiments were found to be 1.55 and 1.22 for BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903 maize genotypes respectively whereas the mean of the diffusion coefficients (D), obtained viz. $0.0651 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 0.0556×10^{-5}

Table 1. Seed constants (β_{Seed}) of maize (*Zea mays*. L) genotypes

Sl. no.	Maize genotype	$\beta_{\text{Seed}} \times 10^3$
1.	BH-660	105.1
2.	Pop-902 \times 903	132.2
3.	Paras ^a	233.3
4.	Parkash ^a	175.6
5.	Parbhat ^a	125.6
6.	Kesri ^a	140.5

^aIndian maize genotypes.

$\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ differed by $0.0095 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Thus the diffusion coefficients obtained by Phillips¹ for different varieties of crops resulted in somewhat different values. The \bar{D} values obtained in the present case for BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903 has clearly shown the possible variation in the determination of \bar{D} values when the final weights of seeds are taken with and without wiping them. So the best alternative seems to be to determine \bar{D} by two replicated experiments, one when the final weight is taken without wiping and the other after wiping the seed and then the mean of these two \bar{D} may give the most appropriate value for uniformly and reproducibility.

In the present study the \bar{D} values obtained for BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903 genotypes without and after wiping the seeds are recorded in the last column of Table 2 and the mean \bar{D} values are also tabulated for comparison. From these results it can be inferred that the mean \bar{D} values viz. $0.0651 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.0556 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ obtained for the above genotypes are comparable in the order of magnitude not with each other but also with those obtained (Phillips¹) for corn varieties viz. $(0.0139-0.0222) \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 28 °C. This fact also further supported the validity of the theory of water diffusivity⁹ based on the particle density gradient rather than concentration and water potential gradient as proposed by Slayter¹¹. Further a comparison of the mean \bar{D} values of both the genotypes showed that diffusivity of BH-660 is approximately 1.2 times that of Pop-902 \times 903 at 25 °C. On the average BH-660 absorbed nearly 11.1% more water than the Pop-902 \times 903 maize seed.

(iii) *Co-relation between the critical time for germination (t_{crg}) with diffusivity and enhancement of germination :*

The diffusivity values (Table 2) for the two maize

genotypes were determined under the steady-state conditions at 25 °C and which were attained at 136 h and 63 h for the BH-660 and Pop-902 \times 903 genotypes respectively. In order to co-relate the above time of steady-state with the critical time for germination [which is now defined⁹ as the time when the seed(s) soaked in water attained the critical moisture content and is at the peak of biochemical and physiological activities necessary for proper germination and which is/are different from the time of germination (t_g) as reported and estimated for soybean, corn and cotton seed¹], field germination trails were performed with bulk seeds for the above varieties. Bulk seeds from the same lots for each genotypes with variable weights were selected at random and subjected to water diffusion experiments at 25 °C for the same time for which steady-state conditions were achieved. Clean stopper glass bottles of 1 litre capacity filled with de-ionized water and bulk seeds of each genotypes soaked in it were employed for the diffusion experiments at 25 °C. Although seeds randomly selected were of different weights for each genotype it was assumed that variation in \bar{D} values for any single seed in the bulk were negligible since, time 't' in eq. (2) is in denominator and is in seconds. After soaking the bulk seeds of each genotypes for the same period of time viz. steady-state time, they were immediately sown in randomized experimental plots in three replications. The germination were recorded after ten days and it was found that 87% and 68% seeds germinated and seedlings emerged in comparison to 79% and 66% in case of control experiments (in which only unsoaked seeds were sown and the replications were also three). The above enhancement in percent germination clearly show that the critical time for germination (t_{crg})

Table 2. Initial and final amount of water (g), the number of water molecules, quantities ΔN_0 and ΔN_f and the \bar{D} at 25 °C

Maize genotype		W_1 (g)	W_2 (g)	W_3 (g)	W_4 (g)	$\times 10^{-23}$				ΔN_0	ΔN_f	$\bar{D} \times 10^5$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
						N_1	N_2	N_3	N_4			
BH-660	Without wiping	12.9619	0.0307	12.7256	0.2363	4.333	0.0103	4.2544	0.0790	4.3227	4.1754	0.0675
	After wiping	12.9619	0.0307	12.7411	0.2208	4.333	0.0103	4.2596	0.0738	4.3227	4.1858	0.0627
	Mean	12.9619	0.0307	12.7333	0.2285	4.333	0.0103	4.2570	0.0764	4.3227	4.1806	0.0651
Pop-902 \times 903	Without wiping	12.9619	0.0222	12.8376	0.1243	4.333	0.0074	4.2919	0.0416	4.3260	4.2503	0.0588
	After wiping	12.9619	0.0222	12.8498	0.1121	4.333	0.0074	4.2960	0.0375	4.3260	4.2585	0.0524
	Mean	12.9619	0.0222	12.8437	0.1182	4.333	0.0074	4.2940	0.0396	4.3260	4.2544	0.0556

of the maize genotypes is the time when steady-state conditions were achieved (viz. 136 h and 63 h) and during which the seeds attained the critical moisture content and optimum biochemical and physiological activities necessary for proper germination. In other words with the mean diffusivity values of 0.0651×10^{-5} and 0.0556×10^{-5} (all in $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) and critical time for germination (t_{ctg}) of 136 h, and 63 h at 25 °C for the above maize varieties, percentage germination were found to be enhanced as compared to control experiments for the maize genotypes. On the basis of the above study it can be inferred that the diffusion theory recently proposed⁹ can be successfully applied for determining water diffusivities in germination seeds of crops and the diffusion technology developed can be fruitfully exploited for estimating the time for germination and for enhancing seed germination.

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